

TELEMEDICINE AS A TOOL TO MANAGE PATIENTS WITH POORLY CONTROLLED TYPE 2 DIABETES MELLITUS: A QUALITY IMPROVEMENT PROJECT

Alicia Calzada, DNP, RN, FNP; Beverly Quaye, Ed.D. RN, PHN, NEA-BC, FACHE; Penny Weismuller, DrPH, RN

Background

- The number of patients with diabetes mellitus type 2 (DMT2) continues to rise. The incidence is 1.5 million US adults per year.
- The Healthy People 2020 diabetes' goal was to reduce the disease and its economic burden, as well as to improve the quality of life of people with diabetes.
- Telemedicine as a tool to manage DMT2 has proven to be more effective than the usual care in managing diabetes.

Problem Statement

The problem this quality improvement (QI) project addresses is the need to improve poorly controlled diabetes mellitus (PCDM) outcomes for patients by utilizing telemedicine as a tool.

Project Purpose

The purpose of this QI project is to evaluate the effectiveness of adding telemedicine to usual care for PCDM patients at an outpatient clinic.

Methods

- Design: QI project guided by the IHI Model for Improvement, whose interventional steps were aligned with the PDSA cycle
- Setting: Private outpatient clinic located in Norwalk, California
- Sample: 25 patients who were diagnosed with PCDM, between 40-65 years of age
- Measures: HgbA1C, Logs: fasting blood glucose (FBG), exercise, medication compliance, and diet

Theoretical Framework

The Model for Improvement (MI) Three Questions asked:

1. *What are we trying to accomplish?*
Improve A1C values with the use of telemedicine
2. *How will we know that a change is an improvement?*
By measuring A1C values and data from logs (BG, diet, medication and exercise)
3. *What change can we make that will result in an improvement?*
Continue with telemedicine

PDSA Cycle

Plan

- Gather team: FNP (author), Care Coordinator (CC), Management Assistant (MA), and Clinic Manager (CM)
- Plan televisit appointments and data collection (A1C & Patient Logs) on 25 PCDM patients
- Plan predictions and timeline

Do

- MA/CC/CM: Schedule telemedicine visits
- FNP: Data collection (A1C and Pt Logs)
- FNP: Data review

Study

- FNP: Analyze data
- Summary of findings (Results)
- Determined that an improvement was made

Act

- FNP: Analyze data
- Summary of findings (Results)
- Determined that an improvement was made

Limitations

- COVID-19 pandemic interfered with the patients' abilities to receive follow-up care with laboratory (A1C) and specialty referrals.
- No telemedicine policies or procedures are in place at the clinic.

Discussion

- The results were consistent with the literature in that telemedicine is an effective tool to manage patients with poorly controlled diabetes.
- The results showed a decrease in medication non-compliance, a reduction in daily carb consumption of over 40%, an increase in exercise >150 min a week, a decrease in FBG >130 after 2 months of telemedicine.
- Diet and exercise were the most challenging factors patients faced. Many patients consumed an excess of the recommended carbohydrates and struggled to meet the exercise guidelines.

Recommendations

- PCDM patients could benefit from regular telemedicine monitoring.
- Implement an integrated system with closer monitoring for follow up with specialty care (nutrition, endocrine referrals).
- Telemedicine policies and procedures would be beneficial for clinic staff.

Conclusion

- As the incidence of diabetes increases, improved access to diabetes care is necessary.
- Telemedicine appears to be an effective care delivery method in the management of PCDM in an outpatient clinic setting.

Results

